

A Study on Effects on E-Recruitment System Model in Tamilnadu

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Abstract

Recruitment marketing is growing and is emerging as one of the top trends in today. The objectives of this study mainly focus on the rapidly changing technological world, The companies who adopt innovations are the one that merely succeeds. This research focus on effects on e-recruitment system model on IT companies only on geographical area of tamilnadu. The research design is exploratory in nature with the total population of 17, 48, 000 in tamilnadu and actual sample size was around 400 employees (Umasekaran, 2008 source) were stratified random sampling techniques was adopted. In the paper web based recruitment, the companies can benchmark the e- recruitment application from wider perspectives on use of AI and BD in developing business analytical tools for eliminating bias and for quality retention of employees. This research proposal mainly encompasses the research needed to propose a structure framework of E-Recruitment with the tool of structure equation modeling Using AMOS (Analysis of moment structure) software with on perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, and enjoyment on intention to use e – recruitment. Also to identify the impact of intermediate variable as attitude towards BD and AI on e – recruitment. It is indeed the need of the hour for all the recruiters to adopt the change in the recruitment practices. In order to catch up the pace with the youth population of Tamil Nadu.

Keyword: *Artificial intelligence, Structural Equation Modelling*

Introduction

The purpose of this study is to develop and understanding of how recruiting has evolved and the ramification that E- recruitment has on the recruitment process.

E-recruitment is a relatively new phenomenon, so the author will try connecting the dots of how traditional recruitment process evolved to the modern day recruitment process using social media.

Objectives

1. To study the trends in e-recruitment uses and practices.
2. To test the model frame with on perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, enjoyment on intention to use e-recruitment.
3. To identify the impact of intermediate variable as attitude towards using on intention of use e-recruitment.

Scope

- This study mainly focuses only on IT companies.
- This study focuses on geographical area of tamilnadu.
- In IT company the sample size will be taken only from company practicing e-recruitment

Review of Literature

Artificial Intelligence: How It Can Help HR Professionals. Authors: Kappes, Chris. Source: Orange County Business Journal. 12/3/2018, Vol. 41 Issue 49, pB-44-B-44. 1p. Document Type: Article.

Subjects: Human resources department Artificial intelligence occupation computer software. Business turnover: Abstract: The article reports on the benefits of artificial intelligence for human resources (HR) Professionals. It mentions that AI uses past data to learn and improve its own processes, it can take the past information gathered on various jobs, measuring how various candidates do after they're hired. It states that HR departments and recruiting firms that have adopted AI software to aid in recruitment have experienced significantly reduced costs per hire, as well as decreases in turnover. ISSN: 1051-7480, Accession Number:133541359.Database: Data base :Regional Business News.

Recruit Better Data Analysts. Authors: Forsyth, John1Moorman, Christine2 Spittle's, Steven3 Source: Harvard Business Review Digital Articles. 2/14/2014, p2-3. 2p. Document Type: Article. Subject Terms: *Employee recruitment*Computer systems analysts*Big data

Abstract: The article discusses several strategies by companies of any size to improve their recruitment of big data analysts such as using more specific language, using an always on approach to recruiting, and enhancing management's analytical skill. Author Affiliations:1Partner at McKinsey & Company in the Stamford office. Professor of Business Administration at the Fuqua School of Business, Duke University 3Partner at McKinsey & Company in the Brussels office. ISSN: 0100-0004. Accession Number:118584103. Database: Business Source Elite.

Summary of Literature

An Optical Character Recognition (OCR) device then converts the scanned material into basic format, upon which the system's artificial intelligence reads the text and extracts key data, such as name, skills, qualifications, and experience. Artificial Intelligence enhances the ability for big data analytics. Big data on real-time basis that holds the promise for intelligence and insights.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the most appropriate method to be used to find reliable and credible result for the research objective. The research design is the exploratory in nature within which research is conducted blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. Sampling techniques used in this method are random techniques.

Data Collection

The primary data for the research study were collected through structured questionnaire. Secondary data are those, which are already collected and recorded. Secondary data was collected from journals, magazines, newspapers, manuals of the company and websites.

- SAMPLE SIZE: 400 employees (umasekaran, 2008 source)
- TOTAL POPULATION: 17,48,000
- The sample size for the study is fixed at 400 of employees
- For the purpose of sampling the researcher has conducted a study on 400 employees in IT companies and the study on effects of e-recruitment in tamilnadu.
- The tools used for the analysis are structural equation modeling using AMOS software.
- Final thought on using bigdata and artificial intelligence in e-recruitment.
- The tools used for the analysis are structural equation modeling using AMOS software.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The purposed model of study includes big data and artificial intelligence in e-recruitment

Novelty in Research Proposal

Bigdata recruiting makes the hiring process faster because of the velocity at which it recognizes and evaluates information.

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